

Research Report in Business and Its Related Areas Writing Style

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Abstract

Research is very important for every business areas. It is always bring the quality or improving the quality in the field of the subject stream. When we follow the standard format for writing the research report, it brings the quality and enhancement also it can be traced out the errors and mistakes. In the research world, there are numerous formats which are framed and followed by the different authors and different institutions based on their research study and problem. Here, the authors have some intentions to support the formats for writing style which bring the quality. In this review article, designing of standard research format in business and related areas mentioned which may be followed in the research proposal and the final research report of business and its related areas. The intention of the article is to bring the quality research in the areas of the fields through the appropriate format which related to the study.

Keywords: Standard Business Research Format; Research Design; Research Methodology in Business and Business Related Areas.

Introduction

Research is very important for every business areas. It always brings the quality/improve the quality in the field of the subject. When we follow the standard format for research, it bring the quality, it can be traced out the errors and mistakes. There are numerous format has been framed and followed by the different authors and different institutions. Here, the author has some intentions to support the formats to bring the quality. In this general articles of the designing of standard research framework in business and related areas mentioned what may be followed in the research proposal and the final research report.

In The Research Writing Format the Important Points to be Remembered .They are as Follows,

1. The Title Must be Very Specific
2. In the first Chapter, Introduction – in the introduction, it must start with some famous quotes by the world famous authors in the word. The important points of the research topic must be mentioned with citation and references in the footnote.
3. The contents may be followed in the first chapter
 - a. Introduction
 - b. Important or Significant of the Study
 - c. If it is a proposal, few review of related literature can be mentioned here.

- d. Statement of the problem – In the statement of the problem the problem must be narrowed down. The variables must be mentioned and its must be explained with the purpose. [The variables may be dependent and independent variables which also depends upon the nature of the research work. The specific research questions can be asked or raised for each and every aspect of the variables.
 - e. Objectives of the Study – The objectives must be focused the purpose which should have a significant with the topic. There must be a general and specific objectives.
 - f. Scope of the Study or the areas of the study
 - g. Methodology – In this methodology part it can be followed Data Requirements, Research Design, Primary Data Collection Techniques, Secondary Data Collection Techniques, Sampling procedure, Sample Size, Sample Techniques (with Tabulations), Statistical tools used for the analysis and its purpose, Data Analysis
 - h. Framework of your study – Mention in diagram, chart, pictures or texts.
 - i. Research Outcome/Hypothesis
 - j. Definition and Terms Used (Variables/parameter/factors must be explained it)
 - k. Profile of the study
 - l. Valuation of the analysis and interpretation of thesis
 - m. Limitations of the Study
 - n. Time Schedule/Gantt Chart/Itinerary of Work
 - o. Budget
 - p. Chapter Schemes
 - q. Conclusions/Summary
4. In the Second Chapter. It must be related to the review of the literature. How to write the review of related literature. If it is mentioned in the following points it may be more effective to defend your research topic. They are as follows.
- a. There must be an Introduction
 - b. The related literature must be segregated based on the Topic/Statement of the problems variables/Objectives. It must have collected from the various studies, from the world, continent, country and region level. Should not mentioned more from the books. It may be used little bit at the beginning. Example,

An attempt has been made to review the literature of earlier studies. Few studies had been conducted in the field of housing problem, housing policies and programmes of different countries with different objectives by different researchers. The present study deviates from that of the earlier studies as, it focuses attention on rural, urban housing, housing policy and its implications. The relevant studies are being presented in the following pages.

Eugene, C. Staley, (1954) in his study, most of the people does not have a constructed house. Their houses have lack of facilities like electricity, mud wall, no taps for water, poor structure which are very dangerous to live in.¹
 - c. Every segregation atleast you have to write 10 studies at Ph.D level, 3 at Post Graduate Level, 1 at Undergraduate level each like with the above example. There must be a conclusion/summary in this chapter too. There must be a footnote in each and every study with citation too.

¹Eugene, C. Staley, "The Future of Underdeveloped Countries", New York, 1954, p.14.

The following ways would be the better if the researcher mentioning the review of literature with arguments, elements of the argument and discovery and advocacy of argument.

- Definition of key words or phrases used in literature.
- Conceptual frame work/theoretical background of the research title
- The need (use) of the research title in :
 - ⇒ World
 - ⇒ Continent
 - ⇒ National
 - ⇒ Study area
- The Current issues of the title at,
 - ⇒ World
 - ⇒ Continent
 - ⇒ National
 - ⇒ Study area
- Policy/Programme/Problem to implement the research title at,
 - ⇒ World
 - ⇒ Continent
 - ⇒ National
 - ⇒ Study Area
- Empirical/Experimental/descriptive/analytical study was conducted on the research title in,
 - ⇒ World
 - ⇒ Continent
 - ⇒ National
 - ⇒ Study Area

5. The third chapter may be the international and continent, national, region level of the scenario of the topic. That means what is the past and present scenario of the topic. The title may be International, Continent, National and Region Scenario. In this chapter also there must be an Introduction and Conclusion/Summary
6. The fourth Chapter may be Analysis and Interpretations.
There can/may be Part A and Part B, etc. Part A must be analyzing the secondary (Quantitative data relating to your objectives) using the generic and inferential statistics. Part B must be analyzing the primary data using the generic and inferential statistics. In this chapter also you can write the introduction and conclusion/summary.
7. The fifth chapter might be Findings, Suggestions, Recommendations, conclusion and suggestions of the future study. It must be useful to the concern body.
8. Bibliography and References – This must be at the second last of your report/proposal. It may be from Books, Journals, Proclamations and Reports, Thesis/Dissertations, Magazines, News Papers, Manuals and websites with the Harvard format or American Physiological Association format.
9. Annexure – This may be at the end of the report. This may be your questionnaire, interview schedule, etc. Data used it for your analysis.
10. General points/ guidelines.

Throughout the thesis there must be citations and footnotes if possible. There must be a significant between topic, statement of the problems, objectives, hypothesis, review of literatures, scenario, analysis and interpretations, finding, suggestions, recommendations, conclusion and suggested topic and areas of the

future study. The data may be presented in table, chart and graph with source(s). The sources must be mentioned if you have taken a data for your analysis purpose. There must be a coherence, sequence with your own style of English language.

Other Important Points to Remember When writing Research Report

Research Ethics

- ❖ Integrity and quality
- ❖ Informed about the purpose, methods, uses of research work
- ❖ Respecting confidentiality and anonymity
- ❖ Participation should be voluntary
- ❖ Harm to participants should be avoided
- ❖ Research should be independent
- ❖ Any conflict of interest or partiality should be explicit

Selection of Funding Body

- ❖ What are their objectives and criteria?
- ❖ What will they offer?
- ❖ What types of programme are they offering?
- ❖ Who are their stakeholders?
- ❖ Who are their peer reviewers?
- ❖ Will you have the freedom to publish?
- ❖ What about ownership of intellectual property?
- ❖ What strings are attached?

Characteristics of Your Research

- ❖ Original idea/originality of thought
- ❖ Imaginative approach
- ❖ Unique and relevant questions
- ❖ Important phenomenon
- ❖ Exciting conceptual advance

Writing Skills of Your Research Must Show

- ❖ Demonstrated knowledge & critical analysis of relevant work by others
- ❖ Appropriate experimental, theoretical and/or modeling approaches
- ❖ Focused project plan with contingencies
- ❖ Experience in methodology and techniques
- ❖ Feasibility demonstrated
- ❖ Track record
- ❖ Demonstrated potential

Intellectual Merit Criterion

- ❖ Importance in advancing knowledge and understanding in own field or across different fields
- ❖ Is the individual or team well qualified to conduct the project?
- ❖ Extent of suggesting and exploring creative and original concepts
- ❖ Is it well conceived and organized

- ❖ Is there sufficient access to resources?

Broader Impacts Criterion

- ❖ Integrating research and education
- ❖ Broadening the participation of underrepresented groups
- ❖ Enhancing the infrastructure for research and education
- ❖ Disseminating results broadly to enhance scientific and technological understanding
- ❖ Benefits of the activity to society

Conclusions

Research is very important for every business areas. It always brings the quality/improve the quality in the field of the subject. When we follow the standard format for research, it brings the quality and can trace out the errors, mistakes and omissions. There are numerous formats that have been framed and followed by the different authors and different institutions. Here, the format is mentioned as above. The author has some intentions to support the formats to bring the quality for the research work. In this general article of writing style of research report/designing of standard research framework in business and related areas may be followed in the research proposal and the final research report where necessary. The intention of the descriptive research article is to ensure the quality research in areas/fields in business and its related areas.

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